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Digital Rights Management (DRM) in the Libraries of Digital-era: Concepts, IPR Issues & Concerns of LIS Community

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Abstract

A rapid shifting perceived from traditional content to digital media due to increasing advantages in every step of the information life cycle: create, collect, organize, store, access, deliver & use. Along with the advantages, digital content transactions are more likely prone to effects through IPR issues. Copyright and intellectual property rights (IPR) have been established and extended over hundreds of years, but implementing the same in the digital environment faces huge challenges. This article started by introducing digital rights & digital rights management (DRM), its architectural framework & techniques, and associated IPR issues. The perception of the LIS community about the role & responsibility of users & library professionals to solve these problems are the main focus of the latter part. A short survey is conducted using Google form questionnaire (N=238) and targeted all four categories, namely, LIS students (100 or 40%), LIS research scholars (25 or 10%), LIS faculties (18 or 85) & Library professionals (95 or 32%); to get the perception of the LIS community. The targeted experimental documents are categories of digital contents by their origin (i.e. Born, Turn & Gain digital documents). The geographical scope of the study extends beyond India to include some international viewpoints as well. In responses, no of the female respondent (131 or 55%) is slightly higher than male respondents (107 or 45%), while the majority of responses came from the Punjab state (42 or 19.72%). The survey findings suggested that Online materials (113 or 50.90%) Turn digital documents (168 or 75.68%) are more likely prone to IPR issues. Among users' responsibilities, "Use of proper acknowledgement, referencing & citation" is the most preferred one (221 or 99.55%) and "Arrange orientation & outreach programme regarding IPR issues" is indicated as the major responsibility (212 or 95.50%) of the library professionals.

Keywords: Digital rights, Digital rights management, DRM, DRM architecture, DRM techniques, Intellectual property rights, IPR, Users' responsibility, Library professionals responsibility

1. Introduction:

With the invention of new-age ICT infrastructure, the global information explosion makes it difficult for the information provider to manage information and disseminate it ethically. Digital Rights Management poses one of the toughest challenges for content communities in this digital age. Traditional rights management of physical materials benefited from the materials' physicality as this provided some barrier to unauthorized exploitation of content (Iannella, 2001). However, it is already noticed a serious breach of copyright law because of the ease with which digital files can be copied and transmitted. Unethical use of information gradually increase the financial loss of content provider and has a negative impact on the willingness of multimedia content providers to endorse the distribution of their documents in a networked environment. It leads to destroying the opportunity to flourish new concepts & ideas.

Although copyright laws protect online information, monitoring the Internet and finding and punishing lawbreakers is extremely challenging (Arsenova & Rwth-Aachen, 2006). Unfortunately, technology alone will not make it possible; rather, ethical awareness programmes and responsibility reminders will help to awaken digital content users by developing a sense of future returns.

2. Literature Review

Prior research on intellectual property rights (IPRs), associated concerns, and their application and challenges in the digital medium are discussed here. Such previous literature study also aids in understanding the topics that have already been explored as well as the gaps that exist between such studies.

Mir (2016) provided an overview of IPR issues & challenges in the digital environment, as well as the role of librarians in the protection of copyright literature in the digital environment. The study also focused on patrons need towards understanding IPR laws in using library services without infringement with the advancement of technology and strong understanding & awareness about IPRs by the users. By mentioning historical background, development of digital libraries and introducing IPR in a digital environment, **Handa & Bhatt (2015)** offered an overview of some significant IPR issues specific to the library community in the Indian digital environment. **Baraliuc et al. (2012)** examined the ratification process of the Anti-Counterfeiting Trade Agreement (ACTA) in the European Union. This agreement raised many (academic and non-academic) questions on various aspects of IPR, one of which is the relationship between copyright enforcement and the fundamental rights of (alleged) infringers in this digital environment. **Niqresh's study (2018)** focused on identifying the most significant intellectual issues in web resource selection and acquisition, source indexing, communication and management of intellectual property rights, electronic resource production and availability, and digital resource maintenance. In conclusion, the study stated that, whether there are new or modern trends in library issues, libraries are able to stand and cope with all the modern technology. **Tamilselvan & Balasubramanian (2012)** mainly discussed the developments to establish a digital library, problems of use & access to digital technology and electronic information over the internet. The study clearly explains the nature of copyright violations in the digital environment, including databases, as well as the disparities in legislation and the impact of the internet. Further, it mentioned techniques, namely cryptography, digital watermarks & digital signatures for effective control of rights infringement in various environments, as well as the security of information over networks and multimedia works. The study ends by posing several significant considerations about the usage of digital data. In a similar study, **Chattopadhyay (2016)** investigated the extent and coverage of numerous IPR concepts, e.g. patents, copyright, designs, trademarks, computer software, databases, Internet, and cyber laws. The main focus of the study is on copyright concerns related to digital/electronic information and the preservation of digital rights. Libraries provide access to digital material through a variety of legal constructs; license agreements, exceptions under national copyright law, legal deposit, and the public domain. Digital rights management (DRM) poses a threat. **Hombal & Prasad (2012)** attempted to introduce the issues concerning copyright protection in the digital library environment. The paper of **Sanjaya (2021)** tried to investigate IPR issues in cyberspace, with a focus on trademark infringement via abusive domain name registrations. The paper further examined the trademark-domain name interface, including parallels and differences, regions of conflict, and an examination of existing dispute resolution methods, as well as recommendations for improvements.

3. Study Rationale:

All of the studies above investigated different aspects of copyrights & related rights in digital medium, in relation with dissemination of information through digital library, its Indian & European scenario and so

on. However, no such research has been conducted specifically concentrating on Born, Turn & Gain digital contents, IPR issues related to such digital document accession & transfer and the responsibility of digital media users & library professionals on this area.

4. Study Objectives:

After thoroughly analyze the past researches & determined the study rationale, the objectives of the present study identifies as follows,

- (i) To provide a brief understanding of digital contents by creation: Born digital, Turn digital & Gain digital
- (ii) To illustrate basic aspects of digital rights, digital rights management (DRM), its architectural framework & techniques.
- (iii) To identify IPR issues pertaining to digital media (case specific: Born, Turn & gain digital contents)
- (iv) To identify the users' responsibility in relation to IPR issues in digital media
- (v) To identify the role of Library professionals in relation to IPR issues in digital media

5. Methodology:

The current research is divided into two sections: Theoretical Overview & Response Analysis. The layout of the theoretical segment was designed to understand the actual problem of IPR in digital media. This section started with a description of digital contents (according to creation path), digital rights, DRM (DRM architecture, DRM approaches) and so on. Further, it provides a complete understanding of the readers about the IPR concerns and a deeper grasp of the survey section of the study, even can correlate & compare its findings with their own perception.

To evaluate the awareness level & perception of the LIS community about such IPR issues in the digital environment, a short survey in conducted with the help of an online questionnaire built with Google form (available at: <https://forms.gle/Wo4wu7e43d8LyyRv7>) and distributed among four targeted groups of LIS community namely: LIS students, LIS research scholars, LIS faculties & Library staffs; both online & printed form, as the case demand. The questionnaire covered three types of close-end questions: yes-no types, multiple-choice & multi-selection categories. The survey mainly targeted the types of digital content disguised by its origin path. The survey took almost 6 months (*May 2021 - Oct. 2021*) and distributed over 350 targeted sample groups of which 238 (response rate: 68.00%) took part in this survey from a different region of India and also from outside the India.

6. Theoretical Overview of the Study:

6.1. Digital Contents:

The very word “digital” has acquired a status that far exceeds its humble dictionary definition (Earnshaw & Vince, 2001). In general, a document can be categorized as a digital document if it exists in digital format (as a string of bits) in its present form, which can be transmitted across the internet, and then re-distributed, copied, and stored in perfect digital form. This researchers focused at digital contents that were divided into three categories based on their origin of creation: Born Digital, Turn Digital, and Gain Digital.

Born Digital contents are those that have been created as digital format from the origin. Turn Digital contents are not created in a digital format from the origin, but are converted to digital content afterwards

from paper-based print form. Gain Digital contents are obtained from other sources and are currently available in a digital format; nevertheless, the source of origin is unclear or unknown.

6.2. Digital Rights:

Individuals’ human and legal rights to access, use, produce, and publish digital media or to access and use computers, other electronic devices, and telecommunications networks, are known as digital rights. In the context of digital technology, particularly the Internet, the concept of digital rights is particularly relevant to the protection and fulfilment of existing rights, such as the right to privacy and freedom of expression (TechTarget, 2017). The laws of several countries recognize a right to Internet access (Lucchi, 2011).

6.3. Digital Rights Management (DRM)

According to the Encyclopedia Britannica online, “digital rights management (DRM), protection of copyrighted works by various means to control or prevent digital copies from being shared over computer networks or telecommunications networks” (Gregersen, 2019). DRM became necessary when piracy & infringement caused publishers and digital content providers to lose a significant amount of capital due to a failure in their return on investment. For-profit publishers and vendors worldwide banded together to develop the required countermeasures to combat such piracy and infringement and protect their legal rights to their creation. In online databases, the DRM technologies have enabled publishers to enforce access policies that not only disallow copyright infringements, but also prevent lawful fair use of copyrighted works, or even implement use constraints on non-copyrighted works that they distribute. (Hombal & Prasad, 2012)

6.3.1. DRM Architecture

There is no unified DRM architecture; instead, different content providers offer a variety of frameworks as per their content dissemination framework. This section of the study addresses the Functional and Information Architecture domains and summarise the current state of DRM technologies and information architectures.

- a) **DRM Functional Architecture:** The overall functional DRM architecture shown in Figure 1 is appropriate for creating digital rights-enabled systems (Arsenova & Rwth-Aachen, 2006).

Figure 1: DRM Functional Architecture (Iannella, 2001)

The overall DRM framework suited to building digital rights-enabled systems can be modeled in three areas:

- **Intellectual Property (IP) Asset Creation and Capture:** to manage the content creation channel so it can be easily traded. This includes asserting rights when content is first created (or reused and extended with appropriate rights to do so) by various content creators/providers.
 - **IP Asset Management:** to manage and enable the trade of content. This includes accepting content from creators into an asset management system. The trading systems need to manage the descriptive metadata and rights metadata (e.g., parties, usages, payments, etc.).
 - **IP Asset Usage:** to manage the usage of content once it has been traded. This includes supporting constraints over traded content in specific desktop systems/software.
- b) **DRM Information Architecture:** The Information Architecture deals with how the entities are modeled in the overall DRM framework and their relationships.

There are three main fractions of the DRM Information model that need to be addressed for a clear understanding:

- **Core Entities Model:** The basic principle of the model is to separate and identify the three core entities: Users, Content, and Rights, as shown in Figure 2. This model implies that any metadata about the three entities needs to include a mechanism to relate the entities to each other.

Figure 2: DRM Information Architecture (Core Entities Model) (Iannella, 2001)

- **Content Model:** It's also necessary to develop a model for the content itself. Many international organisations have attempted to create a model that allows for clearer (i.e., more explicit and/or suitable) attribution of rights information in the past. For example, the FIBR model of the IFLA allows content to be identified at the Work, Expression, Manifestation, and Item layers (IFLA Study Group, 2009).

Figure 3: DRM Information Architecture (Content Model) (Iannella, 2001)

The layers of the Content defined as Work (a distinct intellectual or artistic creation) and Expression (the intellectual or artistic realization of a work) reflect scholarly or creative content. On the other hand, the other layers of Content, defined as Manifestation (the digital embodiment of an expression of work) and Item (a single exemplar instantiation of a manifestation), reflect physical or digital form (see figure 3).

- **Rights Expression Model:** The Rights entity allows expressions to be made about the allowable permissions, constraints, obligations, and any other rights-related information about Users and Content. Hence, the Rights entity is critical because it represents the expressiveness of the language that will be used to inform the rights metadata.

Figure 4: DRM Information Architecture (Rights Expression Model) (Iannella, 2001)

6.3.2. DRM Techniques: DRM can potentially be implemented as a software or hardware solution. Regardless of the type of DRM hardware or software adopted, all content creators who want to protect their data will have to go through an encryption & decryption cycle (see figure 5).

Figure 5: Encryption & Decryption Cycle Diagram of DRM (Hofmeister, 2019)

DRM systems typically include the following techniques:

- **Encryption:** DRM uses a cryptographic algorithm to encrypt content that needs a secret key - a particular phrase or string of numbers. Only the holder(s) of this key can later unlock the content and read it.
- **Public / private keys:** They belong to a family of cryptographic techniques that make use of the one-way nature of certain mathematical functions, resulting in a system where two separate keys are used. They are usually called “public” and “private” keys and each key can be used to encrypt or decrypt data.
- **Digital certificates:** A digital certificate is actually the link between the person and his virtual identity. The digital signatures are issued by certificate authorities that offer guarantees that the public key belongs to the person whose name is in the certificate.
- **Watermarking:** Watermarking is the process of secretly embedding information into a data source in such a way its very existence is hidden.
- **Access control:** Copy protection attempts to find ways for limiting the access to copyrighted material and/or inhibiting the copy process itself.
- **Secure communications protocols:** Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) and Transport Layer Security (TLS) are cryptographic protocols that allow client/server applications to communicate in a way designed to prevent eavesdropping (intercepting of conversations by unintended recipients), tampering and message forgery.
- **Fingerprinting:** Another method to protect digital media is to fingerprint each copy with the subscriber’s information.

- **Hashing:** DRM can protect the digital content from being manipulated by using a so called oneway hash function. A one-way hash function takes digital content of any length as input and produces an output message called a message digest. Any change to the content will produce a completely different message digest. Upon purchasing a digital content on the WEB, in presence of a doubt a customer should be able to check if the content is authentic by performing the one-way hash function and comparing his result with the message digest provided to him from the content provider. If both outputs are the same, the customer can be sure that the obtained content has not been tampered and is authentic.

6.4. IPR Issues Related to Digital Contents

Intellectual property (IP) is a creation of the human intellect that may not have a physical existence but has significant economic worth. Right associated with intellectual property to give it legal protection is referred to as Intellectual Property Right (IPR). (Tamilselvan & Balasubramanian, 2012) In digital environment, Intellectual property law plays a very important role, not just in protecting individuals from the misuse of their know-how, but in promoting originality, creativity and innovation within our society. As designated by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), all five categories of IPRs, namely Copyright & related rights, Patents, Trademarks, Industrial designs & Geographical indications, applicable to digital transformation as well. (Dittmer & Rehaag, 2020)

Two terms can be used to represent IPR concerns in the digital environment: Internet Facilitate & User Generated. Technology advancements can facilitate piracy, counterfeiting, and other IP infringements easier. The continuing development of technology and the global expansion of the Internet have made it easier. The Internet's anonymity and lack of borders create an ideal environment for IP infringement. At the same time, digital content users are confronted with the phenomenon of online user-generated content, mashups, and access to digital culture. Unauthorized data sharing, integration, utilization and public disclosure are the biggest areas of concern.

There are mainly three types of copyright infringements related to IPR issues in digital environments (Attorney Advertising, 2021) (Hombal & Prasad, 2012) (Ahmad & Bag, 2011);

- Direct infringements** - reproduction & redistribution of whole work without a single changes or value addition.
- Contributory infringements** - when a user intentionally encouraged infringement activity and induced or substantially contributed to copyright infringement by another user.
- Vicarious infringements** - when moderator/ supervisor has the ability to guide its users from infringement activity but remain inactive due to some financial or other benefits

7. Survey Section of the Study:

7.1. Population Study:

To distinguish the characteristics of different sample category & their contribution towards this study, the sample population (N=238) at first classified into age & sex, as well as occupation & geographical origin.

7.1.1. Age-wise Distribution:

Age determines the maturity & experience. View-point of different aged people varied a lot, and thus it is important to identify the age distribution of the sample respondents of the study.

Figure 6: Age-wise Distribution of Respondents

According to figure 6, the age of majority of the respondents belongs to 25-30 age group (150 or 63%), followed by 20-24 age group and ≥ 35 age group with 25% (59) & 9% (21) coverage respectively. In this study, among the respondents, the youngest one 21 years old and the oldest one 57 years old. And there are no respondents from 15-19 age group.

7.1.2. Sex-wise Distribution:

The distribution of the population by sex is one of the most significant demographic groupings. It ensure that the study is not gender specific, and valued the perception of all kinds of people despite of their sex & race. As reflected from Figure 7 below, the sample respondents of the study occupy 55% (131) female, 45% (107) male and there is no other category respondent.

Figure 7: Sex-wise Distribution of Respondents

7.1.3. Category-wise Distribution:

Figure 8: Category-wise Distribution of Respondents

In this study the overall four (4) basic categories of samples are selected as target respondents: LIS Students, LIS Research Scholar, LIS Faculty & Library Staff. Out of the 238 respondents, 42% (100) are LIS Students (M.Lib.I.Sc. & B.Lib.I.Sc.), 40% (95) are Library Staff (CL, AL, DL & UL), 10% (25) are LIS Research Scholar (PhD & MPhil) and 8% (18) are LIS Faculty (Asth. Prof., Asso. Prof. & Prof.).

7.1.4. Geographical Distribution:

Figure 9: Geographical Distribution of Respondents

Studying geographical distribution of research sample is important to consider the contribution of different societal population to the study, within a country or globally. Figure 9 displayed that present study consist of 89% (213) Indian respondents and 11% (25) International respondents. Among the 25 International respondents, majority belongs to Bangladesh (8), followed by Sri Lanka (6), Nepal (6) and South Africa (3).

SN	State	No of Respondents (n=213)	Rank
1	Andhra Pradesh	4 (1.88%)	12
2	Gujarat	6 (2.82%)	11
3	Haryana	20 (9.39%)	4
4	Himachal Pradesh	18 (8.45%)	5
5	Jharkhand	3 (1.41%)	13

6	Karnataka	7 (3.29%)	10
7	Kerala	12 (5.63%)	8
8	Madhya Pradesh	31 (14.55%)	2
9	Maharashtra	13 (6.10%)	7
10	Mizoram	2 (0.94%)	14
11	Odisha	2 (0.94%)	14
12	Punjab	42 (19.72%)	1
13	Rajasthan	4 (1.88%)	12
14	Tamil Nadu	22 (10.33%)	3
15	Telangana	1 (0.47%)	15
16	Uttar Pradesh	9 (4.23%)	9
17	West Bengal	17 (7.98%)	6

Table 1: State-wise Distribution of Respondents

Again, according to Table 1, the majority of the Indian respondents were obtained from Punjab state (42 or 19.72%), followed by Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Haryana with 14.55% (31), 10.33% (22) & 9.39% (20) coverage respectively. Important to note that no responses were received from the states not mentioned in table 1.

7.2. Response Analysis & Discussion:

7.2.1. Do you aware of IPR issues related to digital medium?

Awareness	LIS Students (n=100)	LIS Research Scholars (n=25)	LIS Facultyies (n=18)	Library Staffs (n=95)	Total (N=238)
Yes	67 (67.00%)	25 (100.00%)	18 (100.00%)	74 (77.89%)	184 (77.31%)
No	13 (13.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (3.16%)	16 (6.72%)
Not Sure	20 (20.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	18 (18.95%)	38 (15.97%)

Table 2: Awareness about IPR Issues in Digital Medium

This research question is supposed to investigate the awareness of the respondents about the IPR issues in digital medium while accessing digital content. Out of the 238 target respondents, 184 (77.31%) directly indicated that they were aware of IPR issues relating to digital media, whereas 38 (15.97%) were unsure and the other 16 (6.72%) were certain they were not. For this reason, of the 238 target respondents, 222 (93.28%) (aware & unsure ones) were chosen as valid respondents to proceed with the next steps of the survey (*see table 3*).

Validity	LIS Students	LIS Research Scholars	LIS Facultyies	Library Staffs	Total (N=238)
Valid (N _v)	87	25	18	92	222 (93.28%)
Rejected (R)	13	0	0	3	16 (6.72%)

Table 3: Validity of the Sample Respondents

7.2.2. Which document type raised most concerns related to IPR issues in digital medium?

Content Types	LIS Students (n=87)	LIS Research Scholars (n=25)	LIS Faculties (n=18)	Library Staffs (n=92)	Total (N _v =222)
Journal article	33 (37.93%)	6 (24.00%)	5 (27.78%)	44 (47.83%)	88 (39.64%)
Book chapter	3 (3.45%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	13 (14.13%)	16 (7.21%)
Conference papers	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	5 (5.43%)	5 (2.25%)
Online materials	51 (58.62%)	19 (76.00%)	13 (72.22%)	30 (32.61%)	113 (50.90%)

Table 4: Most Concerned Document Types in Digital Medium

This query seeks to determine which document kinds are the most concerned about IPR issues in the digital medium. According to the respondents, online materials are most prone to IPR issues (113 or 50.90%) related to the digital medium, closely followed by journal articles (88 or 39.64%). On the other side, conference papers get the least response (5 or 2.25%) in this regard.

7.2.3. Which type of digital-document raised most concerns related to IPR issues?

Born digital resources are items that are natively created and managed digitally. Turn digital documents are not digitally formed but are turned and managed into digital format with the use of scanners and OCR devices. Gain digital documents are obtained from other sources with unknown creation paths and maybe primarily from born or turn digital contents. (OCLC, 2010)

Digital-document Types	LIS Students (n=87)	LIS Research Scholars (n=25)	LIS Faculties (n=18)	Library Staffs (n=92)	Total (N _v =222)
Born Digital	27 (31.03%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (22.22%)	11 (11.96%)	42 (18.92%)
Turn Digital	51 (58.62%)	25 (100.00%)	14 (77.78%)	78 (84.78%)	168 (75.68%)
Gain Digital	9 (10.34%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (3.26%)	12 (5.41%)

Table 5: Most Concerned Digital-document Types

According to Table 5, among the three types of digital documents by creation, Turn digital documents are the most concerned digital documents (168 or 75.68%) related to IPR issues. Born digital documents sure second place with 18.92% and Gain digital documents are least (5.41%) regarding the same concern.

Now, in order to identify the specific IPR issues that are most concerning among the Born, Turn, and Gain digital documents, Tables 6, 7 & 8 lists the eight (8) most prevalent IPR issues pertaining to each digital content category respectively.

a) IPR issues related to Born Digital contents,

IPR Issues	LIS Students (n=87)	LIS Research Scholars (n=25)	LIS Faculties (n=18)	Library Staffs (n=92)	Total (N_v=222)
Improper or false acknowledgement, referencing & citation	87 (100.00%)	25 (100.00%)	12 (66.67%)	74 (80.43%)	198 (89.19%)
Overlook licensing conditions	61 (70.11%)	12 (48.00%)	7 (38.89%)	63 (68.48%)	143 (64.41%)
Self-plagiarism practice	(9.20%)	6 (24.00%)	14 (77.78%)	17 (18.48%)	45 (20.27%)
Shared copyrighted (closed access) material in open platform	81 (93.10%)	25 (100.00%)	18 (100.00%)	92 (100.00%)	216 (97.30%)
Ignore subscribe database access conditions	25 (28.74%)	13 (52.00%)	6 (33.33%)	90 (97.83%)	134 (60.36%)
Use pirate sites for illegal downloads	6 (6.90%)	21 (84.00%)	0 (0.00%)	58 (63.04%)	85 (38.29%)
Unethical practice while using remote access	11 (12.64%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	43 (46.74%)	54 (24.32%)
Ghost & false authorship	49 (56.32%)	7 (28.00%)	10 (55.56%)	54 (58.70%)	120 (54.05%)

*Shaded areas denoted most preferred IPR issues in each category

Table 6: IPR issues Related to Born Digital Contents

Table 6 displays that for LIS students, “Improper or false acknowledgement, referencing & citation” is the most concerned IPR issue for born digital contents, though LIS research scholars team up with them with 100% coverage for both. Again, “Shared copyrighted (closed access) material in the open platform” is the most concerning IPR issue for LIS research scholars, LIS faculties & Library staff, with 100% coverage for all three. In total, “Shared copyrighted (closed access) material in open platform” is the most concerned IPR issue with 97.30% (216) occupation.

b) IPR issues related to Turn Digital contents,

IPR Issues	LIS Students (n=87)	LIS Research Scholars (n=25)	LIS Faculties (n=18)	Library Staffs (n=92)	Total (N_v=222)
Neglect copyright agreement	74 (85.06%)	25 (100.00%)	18 (100.00%)	92 (100.00%)	209 (94.14%)
Don't collect proper authors' permission	51 (58.62%)	20 (80.00%)	9 (50.00%)	50 (54.35%)	130 (58.56%)
Don't follow fair use policy while digitized	80 (91.95%)	25 (100.00%)	18 (100.00%)	84 (91.30%)	207 (93.24%)
Improper or false acknowledgement, referencing & citation	82 (94.25%)	25 (100.00%)	18 (100.00%)	92 (100.00%)	217 (97.75%)
Unknown author or false author problem	79 (90.80%)	12 (48.00%)	15 (83.33%)	88 (95.65%)	194 (87.39%)
Don't follow restrict	1	0	7	57	65

access condition	(1.15%)	(0.00%)	(38.89%)	(61.96%)	(29.28%)
Don't follow publishers terms & conditions	37 (42.53%)	22 (88.00%)	12 (66.67%)	90 (97.83%)	161 (72.52%)
Problem in change of document format & type after digitization	44 (50.57%)	2 (8.00%)	0 (0.00%)	39 (42.39%)	85 (38.29%)

*Shaded areas denoted most preferred IPR issues in each category

Table 7: IPR issues Related to Turn Digital Contents

Table 7 reveals that the most concerning (all with 100% coverage) IPR issues for turn digital contents are “Neglect copyright agreement”, “Don't follow fair use policy while digitized”, & “Improper or false acknowledgement, referencing & citation”, according to LIS research scholars & LIS faculties. While Library staffs select “Neglect copyright agreement” & “Improper or false acknowledgement, referencing & citation” as most concerned IPR issues with 100% coverage and LIS students only prefers “Improper or false acknowledgement, referencing & citation” with 94.25% coverage. Overall, for turn digital contents, “Improper or false acknowledgement, referencing & citation” is the most concerned (97.75%) IPR issue.

c) IPR issues related to Gain Digital contents,

IPR Issues	LIS Students (n=87)	LIS Research Scholars (n=25)	LIS Faculties (n=18)	Library Staffs (n=92)	Total (N_v=222)
Neglect consortia agreement	49 (56.32%)	16 (64.00%)	11 (61.11%)	51 (55.43%)	127 (57.21%)
Ignore subscribe database access conditions	87 (100.00%)	19 (76.00%)	18 (100.00%)	90 (97.83%)	214 (96.40%)
Exceed download permits	57 (65.52%)	20 (80.00%)	18 (100.00%)	76 (82.61%)	171 (77.03%)
Improper or false acknowledgement, referencing & citation	80 (91.95%)	22 (88.00%)	15 (83.33%)	84 (91.30%)	201 (90.54%)
Shared copyrighted (closed access) material in open platform	85 (97.70%)	25 (100.00%)	16 (88.89%)	92 (100.00%)	218 (98.20%)
Unethical practice while using remote access	44 (50.57%)	0 (0.00%)	5 (27.78%)	56 (60.87%)	105 (47.30%)
Unknown author or false author problem	83 (95.40%)	25 (100.00%)	18 (100.00%)	77 (83.70%)	203 (91.44%)
Problem in identify actual document type	10 (11.49%)	2 (8.00%)	0 (0.00%)	23 (25.00%)	35 (15.77%)

*Shaded areas denoted most preferred IPR issues in each category

Table 8: IPR issues Related to Gain Digital Contents

According to Table 8, for LIS students, “Ignore subscribe database access conditions”; for LIS research scholars, “Shared copyrighted (closed access) material in open platform” & “Unknown author or false author problem”; for LIS faculties, “Ignore subscribe database access conditions”, “Exceed download permits” & “Unknown author or false author problem” and for Library staffs, “Shared copyrighted (closed access) material in open platform” is/are the most preferred IPR issue(s) for gain digital contents,

all with 100% coverage of the particular categories. Again, in the case of total occupation, “Shared copyrighted (closed access) material in open platform” is the most concerned IPR issue for the gain digital contents.

7.2.4. What do you think the responsibility of a user not to create such issues related to IPR while using digital contents?

Every digital media content user should be aware of some basic principles addressing IPR concerns, as well as access and dissemination limitations. Table 9 lists eight (8) different responsibilities to determine which one is preferred by which user type. Because this is a multiple-choice question, respondents can choose more than one responsibility if they like.

Users' Responsibilities	LIS Students (n=87)	LIS Research Scholars (n=25)	LIS Faculties (n=18)	Library Staffs (n=92)	Total (N_v=222)
Required basic knowledge of IPR	55 (63.22%)	17 (68.00%)	13 (72.22%)	69 (75.00%)	154 (69.37%)
Knowledge of copyright licensing before sharing digital document	84 (96.55%)	25 (100.00%)	18 (100.00%)	77 (83.70%)	204 (91.89%)
Use of proper acknowledgement, referencing & citation	87 (100.00%)	25 (100.00%)	18 (100.00%)	91 (98.91%)	221 (99.55%)
Follow publishers conditions while access subscribed database	70 (80.46%)	22 (88.00%)	16 (88.89%)	71 (77.17%)	179 (80.63%)
Stop practicing unethical means while using remote access	46 (52.87%)	11 (44.00%)	7 (38.89%)	92 (100.00%)	156 (70.27%)
Stop using pirated sites for download closed access documents	53 (60.92%)	14 (56.00%)	11 (61.11%)	79 (85.87%)	157 (70.72%)
Should follow fair use restriction in case of printing closed access documents	51 (58.62%)	18 (72.00%)	13 (72.22%)	90 (97.83%)	172 (77.48%)
In case any confusion regarding IPR issues, should contact dept. head or LIS staff	87 (100.00%)	25 (100.00%)	17 (94.44%)	88 (95.65%)	217 (97.75%)

*Shaded areas denoted most preferred users' responsibility in each category

Table 9: Users' Responsibility Regarding IPR issues in Digital Medium

Table 9 identifies that, among the responsibilities, “Knowledge of copyright licensing before sharing digital document” is preferred by LIS research scholars & LIS faculties; “Use of proper acknowledgement, referencing & citation” is preferred by LIS students, LIS research scholars & LIS faculties; “Stop practicing unethical means while using remote access” is preferred by Library staffs only and “In case any confusion regarding IPR issues, should contact dept. head or LIS staff” is preferred by

LIS students & LIS research scholars with 100% coverage in each category. Overall, “Use of proper acknowledgement, referencing & citation” is the most preferred responsibility with 99.55% preference.

7.2.5. What do you think the responsibility of a library professional to solve such issues related to IPR in digital medium?

As a disseminator of information, library professionals have a responsibility to inform their users (of any sort) on the different forms of IPR issues that can occur and the precautions that should be taken when accessing and disseminating digital documents.

Library Professionals Responsibilities	LIS Students (n=87)	LIS Research Scholars (n=25)	LIS Faculties (n=18)	Library Staffs (n=92)	Total (N_v=222)
Arrange orientation & outreach programme regarding IPR issues	80 (91.95%)	22 (88.00%)	18 (100.00%)	92 (100.00%)	212 (95.50%)
While sharing closed access document, licensing agreement should mentioned	69 (79.31%)	14 (56.00%)	8 (44.44%)	41 (44.57%)	132 (59.46%)
Library website should highlight publishers access condition in each subscribed database	84 (96.55%)	19 (76.00%)	12 (66.67%)	87 (94.57%)	202 (90.99%)
Arrange hands-on-training regarding how to give proper reference	72 (82.76%)	25 (100.00%)	18 (100.00%)	59 (64.13%)	174 (78.38%)
Need proper monitoring while provide remote-access services	15 (17.24%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	13 (14.13%)	28 (12.61%)
Should conduct lectures & debates about pros & cons of pirated sites	27 (31.03%)	0 (0.00%)	9 (50.00%)	36 (39.13%)	72 (32.43%)
In providing online DDS or CAS or SDI services, copyright agreement should consider seriously	75 (86.21%)	11 (44.00%)	7 (38.89%)	53 (57.61%)	146 (65.77%)
Should follow fair use policy while providing reprographic & printing services	60 (68.97%)	16 (64.00%)	8 (44.44%)	84 (91.30%)	168 (75.68%)

*Shaded areas denoted most preferred responsibility of library professionals in each category

Table 10: Library professionals’ Responsibility Regarding IPR issues in Digital Medium

Among the eight (8) pre-selected responsibilities of library professionals mentioned in Table 10, “Library website should highlight publishers access condition in each subscribed database” gets the most preference (96.55%) from LIS students; “Arrange hands-on-training regarding how to give proper reference” gets 100% preference from LIS research scholars & LIS faculties; and “Arrange orientation &

outreach programme regarding IPR issues” gets 100% preference from LIS faculties & Library staffs. In total, “Arrange orientation & outreach programme regarding IPR issues” is the most preferred responsibility for the respondents of the study.

8. Findings of the Study:

- a) Digital rights ensures the human & legal rights of digital contents to its creator and digital rights management (DRM) provides architectural framework & techniques to do so.
- b) In digital environment majority of IPR issues originated through Internet facilitation & User generation.
- c) Among the document types online materials are most concerns related to IPR issues in digital medium.
- d) Among the digital-document types (by origin) Turn digital documents are most concerns related to IPR issues in digital medium.
 - Among the born digital documents “Shared copyrighted (closed access) material in open platform” is the major issue concerning IPR problems
 - Among the turn digital documents “Improper or false acknowledgement, referencing & citation” is the major issue concerning IPR problems
 - Among the gain digital documents “Shared copyrighted (closed access) material in open platform” is the major issue concerning IPR problems
- e) “Use of proper acknowledgement, referencing & citation” is indicated as most preferred users’ responsibility by LIS community
- f) “Arrange orientation & outreach programme regarding IPR issues” is indicated as most preferred responsibility of library professionals by LIS community

9. Conclusions & Suggestions:

A common user of digital content comes across intellectual properties from dawn to dusk. He/she may use the products to a large extent under digital rights, mainly because of two possibilities: unintentionally because of lack of IPR awareness or intentionally because of lack of ethical responsibility. The socio-economic development of a country depends to a large extent on the creativity of the people and creative works can’t be encouraged without effective administration of copyright laws. The rapid evolution of digital media and the Internet has had a significant impact on the way how today media is used, distributed, shared, copied and managed. Although this advancement has provided various benefits in the handling of digital content, it has also resulted in changes in electronic data trade and dissemination across networks such as the Internet. In this point, to ensure digital rights, DRM systems enable robust e-commerce, copyright protection, secure distribution and protection of digital data utilizing encryption, watermarking, fingerprints, secure communication protocols, trust infrastructures, etc. Librarians, as custodians of most intellectual property, must draw a clear boundary between information distribution and successful copyright law implementation in the library environment.

Though it should be mentioned that, in DRM, a ‘one size fits all’ rights solution is unlikely. Libraries have a crucial role in the dissemination & preservation of information. However, in acceptance of DRM, some of the information resources will arrive at the library with their embedded rights technology, as e-books do today. Some information resources on the market will have controls that libraries find so unacceptable that they will choose not to obtain those materials. Copyright law also provides the provision of fair use policy to promote easy accessibility & dissemination of information. But, the DRM technologies attempt to control the use of digital media by preventing access, copying or conversion to other formats beyond users. And it is challenging to implement a fair use policy in a digital document already covered under any DRM techniques. Libraries & other content distributors should decide

properly about use & implement copyright policy & DRM techniques in the library without harming their actual responsibility towards the user community.

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